

Living with Brasília: a residents' perspective of the confrontation between heroic vision and social reality

Introduction

Conceived as the symbol of a new era of development and progress, a new way of life and an egalitarian society based on democratic principles, Brasília embodied a spatial order that radically opposed the traditional everyday life in Brazil. The illusion of this new life was everywhere reinforced in the modernist city, transforming Brasília's project not only in a political, but also in a heroic social project.

To what extent do the residents understand the effect of the modernist design on their way of life and on their ability to appropriate the city? What is the actual relationship the inhabitants have with the modernist city? Have any significant changes in the way people appropriate modernist structures occurred since they were implemented?

This paper discusses everyday life in the modernist city and its contribution to the production of city space through the analysis of the appropriation of space in three residential areas of the Federal District, the urban area formed by the Pilot Plan of Brasília and the satellite towns. The aim is to offer an interpretation of the genesis of the user's own space in the modernist city.

A superblock was selected in the Pilot Plan – the 312 North – because this type of housing scheme constitutes the predominant mode of the modernist city. The other two areas are located in two satellite towns, the Block 8 in Sobradinho, and the Block 431 in Samambaia, which area satellite towns that have

residential areas with a modernist design. These areas embody similar design concepts and their design present the same characteristics existing also in the majority of the other housing areas of each area where they are located. The extensive presence of the highways, the elimination of the traditional streets formed by the façades of the buildings and the new conception of space that radically changed the proportion of voids and grounds in the urban space introduced to the Brazilians an urban space radically different to what they were accustomed to live in and provoked different reactions.

Significant changes have occurred up to the present days in the relationship the residents have with their environment, especially those that occurred after they established an intimate link with the city. This intimate link has been established through a process of identification that allowed the residents to feel a cultural belonging related to these areas, leading them to a process of appropriation of their space.

After four decades of existence, Brasília is rather different from the city the planners intended to be. What has been attained by the popular restructuring of Brasília is a peculiar urban setting that, although to some extent it keeps modernist characteristics, it also reproduces the spatial and social organization common to other Brazilian cities.

Today, behind Brasília's monumental modernist appearance, lies a city that has been physically and symbolically rearranged by its residents. This has allowed them to transform the rigid modernist structure into a living city that seems to be fully acceptable by them.

Housing Areas: a brief description

The superblocks, which are the predominant mode of dwellings in the modernist city, introduced a new concept of space in a residential area. They are self-sufficient areas with their own facilities such as an elementary school, medical services, a child care unit, recreation and some commercial units. Each superblock is linked to three of its neighbors by shared facilities. Its design proposes the ultimate segregation between the vehicular and pedestrian traffic. The traditional street formed along the façades of the buildings is eliminated, and there is a predominance of the green areas and an easy accessibility to all through the ground floor of the buildings.

The commercial buildings, usually situated between two superblocks, originally faced the feeder paths between these superblocks, instead of facing the main road.

Other characteristic typical of this type of residential unit is the presence of huge open spaces that surround the buildings. They usually are green areas of non-descript function, which might suggest expectations that residents would appropriate them freely.

In Sobradinho, the residential areas are divided into different estates sub-divided in several blocks. On each side of the residential blocks are commercial areas as it is in the Pilot Plan.

In the different blocks, the entrances of the houses face a common green area, forbidden to vehicle traffic. Traffic is directed along the street located behind the plots. The backs of the houses face this street that separates one block from another. This design inverts the function of the traditional street, that of being the public outdoor space of sociality.

The residential areas in Samambaia are characterized by a series of blocks that also share common facilities, applying the some system of shared facilities of the Pilot Plan. Many of these facilities have not been built yet, which requires constant struggle by potential users for properly planned and constructed services facilities. The urban design of the residential area is heterogeneous including different public areas, depending on the spatial organization of the plots in the site. The area is connected to the neighborhood by main roads on both sides where the local commercial center is located.

The residents interpreted most of these design characteristics as being in huge contrast to traditional residential set-ups.

Residents' interventions along time: Modernism confronted by the reality of everyday life

These residential areas embody design characteristics that were perceived as quite unfamiliar by the residents. The superblocks suggested a new way of life. The idea was to influence a profound change towards a progressive social integration based on the neighborhood unit.

The residential areas in Sobradinho inverted the function of the street and suggested the users to perform their public social life in green areas that area usually left empty. The residential areas in Samambaia did not provide all the necessary conditions for the performance of the traditional social life required by the users.

The elimination of tradition in the modernist city was not interpreted as an attempt to create an orderly space or resolve the traditional urban chaos in the name of progress and development, but rather as an attempt to neutralize the familiar human crowd and its diverse and dangerous social implications. Interestingly, while the traditional city was conceived as a bastion of chaos, Brazilians in general did not necessarily interpret this as negative. On the contrary, that chaos was perceived as the most valuable expression of urban life, which the modernist city has failed to generate.

The interventions done in the Superblock 312 North range from the residents' demands to pro-

vide venues for social activities, demarcation of territory, change in the uniform visual appearance of the buildings for strengthening local identity, to the appropriation of public areas for private use and to change in the layout of commercial buildings.

The commercial center had their main entrances changed and located facing the main roads that surround the area, where the street movement is, creating an environment quite similar to the existing in other traditional Brazilian cities.

The initial public character of the ground floor of the residential buildings gradually became semi-private. Intended to be an extension of the public area that surrounds the residential buildings, this area was supposed to provide free accessibility to all. The intervention done by the residents denotes their demand of rigid demarcation of individual territory that is a physical expression of conflict between the original intention and the residents' life style.

The residents of Block 8 in Sobradinho spontaneously changed the use of the vehicular street. They usually reach their homes through the back door located in this street. It is here where the residents circulate, chat and meet the neighbors. This contributes to increase intensity of street life in an

environment that originally was not designed for it.

The main entrances to the shops were changed from the feeder road at the edge of the residential area to the main traffic road, similar to what was done in the Pilot Plan.

In Samambaia, most of the changes have to do with demarcation of territory, creation of new spaces for the fulfillment of the demands of the residents, as well as changes in the original layout of the commercial buildings, similar to what happened in the other two areas. The public spaces are often used by some residents to socialize with neighbors, even though there are no proper facilities for such activity. This activity of socializing with neighbors in public spaces that surround the houses replicates again the street life of the traditional Brazilian cities.

The plan's disregard for architectural roots and for traditional social practices had a deep impact on residents, who have struggled ever since to restore the traditional way of life. The architectural and urban elements that support traditional street life, though absent from the modernist city, are nevertheless preserved by the culture, deeply affecting the symbolic meaning and conception of the representational space. Residents took over the city, in spite of the plan's powerful inherent mechanisms for preventing change, and produced their own space within the modernist environment. Out of the popular rebellion against the rigid plan emerged an unpredictable new urban reality in the Federal District.

The changing face of the Federal District

Behind Brasilia's monumental and rigid modernist appearance lies a city that over the past years has been physically and symbolically rearranged by its residents. As a result, they have established an intense emotional bond with their environment. The initial incapacitating feeling of being absorbed by the unfamiliar modernist city was gradually replaced by a sense of home and the satisfaction of being actively involved in the production of space and in the transformation of an alienating space into a familiar and lively environment.

The rearrangement of the city's residential environments is the result of a long process of interpretation and adaptation through continual intervention. The residents have now reclaimed the superblock after its first years as a cold, rationalist environment. The spatial structure of the superblock imposed a collective social life unwanted by the residents. But it forced them to assess and identify their own values, and the residents then began to rearrange their neighborhoods. They transformed the public areas to create a social space, similar to a *barrio*, based on the values of privacy, individuality and diversity. Ironically, a new collective social has now emerged in the superblock, fulfilling the intention of the original plan, but through a different character, to a different tune.

The same values of privacy and diversity were reproduced in the rearrangement of space in the satellite towns. Individuality, however, did not seem to have the same importance for the residents. Here they attempted to create the kind of physical environment necessary for intense social interaction. The residents reproduced the environmental characteristics of a tradition *barrio*, thus infusing their space with traditional meaning. The original attributes that did not motivate social interaction were neutralized by the creation of this new social space.

Brasilia's residents in spite of the rigid character of the modernist plan have created a new urban reality. They have transformed the built environment to reproduce traditional social practices. In so doing they have revived the city's defunct image. Today Brasilia is seen as a city founded on a completely new lifestyle, neither exclusively traditional nor modernist, but rather a synthesis of the two. While the urban chaos of the modernist plan has not been entirely repaired, at least some of the excessive space initially proposed has been eliminated. The residents have infused the rationalist city with a cultural and human dimension embodying the meanings they attach to the space around them. The huge avenues and modern buildings are now interspersed with spaces for social interaction, where people pass by and casually meet others, where

various activities promote exchange between people, where human warmth combats the coldness of the city's reinforced concrete structures. The result is certainly far from the familiar traditional urban space, but it is equally far from the intended rationalist space. What has been generated is a space that, though it retains most of its modernist physical attributes, has been transformed into a living phenomenon that reflects all the social contradictions and conflicts of a society based on diversity.

Conclusions

There have been many debates on modernism and the negative effect of its authoritarian design on peoples' lives. What is of concern in this paper is not the failure or success of modernist urban planning, but the users' interpretation of their audacious city.

The dream of achieving social change through a new spatial order, which was fundamental to the project of Brasilia, no longer has much influence on residents' interpretation of the city.

Brasilia has gradually become a living city capable of satisfying more of its inhabitants' needs. The residents' view of the city has become decidedly positive since they realized they could oppose the authoritarian design and rebuild the city according to their needs. The years of living and contributing to Brasilia have given its residents an emotional bond to the city, and a much more intense relationship with their environment, further motivating them to reinterpret it.

Although the inflexibility of the modernist plan still negatively influences the residents' lives in some respects, their transformation of Brasilia into a living city testifies to the positive effects of active popular opposition to planning rigidity. Social forces infused the modernist city with unexpected events every day, lending it a new intensity, a dynamic urban life, and pointing toward an amodernist horizon.

Brasilia was from the beginning an audacious experiment, the manifestation of modernist urban planning theory. The residents of Brasilia have now acquired for their city a new symbolic significance: the transformation of a modernist urban environment into a living city that reflects in its utilization of space the social contradictions planners tried meticulously to avoid. Moreover, the residents have transformed Brasilia into a city fully acceptable to them, not only because they have regained the freedom to produce their own space, but because of the rewarding feeling of self-empowerment that goes with.

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